

A Comparative Analysis of Teachers' Mode of Training and their Job Performance in Ondo State Primary Schools

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ABSTRACT: The study compared teachers' modes of training and their job performance in Ondo state primary schools. The descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The population of the study comprised all the 11,891 teachers of public primary schools in the study area. The study sample comprised 384 teachers selected from 24 public primary schools using a multi-stage procedure. Two instruments were used to collect data for the study: A Questionnaire titled Teachers' Mode of Training and their Job Performance (TMTJP) which was used to obtain information on the bio-data of the respondents as well as their mode of training and job performance; Teachers' Effectiveness Observation Schedule (TEOS) which was used in observing and rating the teachers while teaching in their classes in the selected schools. Data collected were analyzed using percentage scores. Results indicated that majority of the teachers passed through full-time training 55.47% and a significant proportion 44.53% of the teachers passed through sandwich training. Also, the result showed that the full-time (48.83%) and sandwich-trained teachers (48.53%) had a consistently high level of effectiveness in terms of mastery of subject matter and use of instructional materials in Ondo State primary schools. The study concluded that the full-time trained teachers slightly outperformed their sandwich counterparts in all categories with marginal differences, but with a consistently high level of effectiveness in terms of mastery of subject matter and use of instructional materials in Ondo State primary schools.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Education is a powerful instrument of change, improvement and development. Education also provides a sound basis for individuals to develop their potentialities. As a powerful instrument for effective, productive national change and development, education is generally obtained through teaching and learning. Teachers have been recognized as the main agent of change produced in learners. They play crucial roles in ensuring learners succeed in their chosen career and become forces to reckon with in the country. Report from Digital Class World (2022) establishes the fact that a good teacher helps the learners to become successful human beings. That is, being successful in the society and good citizens of the country. Over the years, the training modes of teachers have remained the nucleus of knowledge and skill acquisition. This is needed for better job performance especially during classroom teaching-learning process. Teachers' modes of training can therefore be rated as a key factor affecting their job performance in the classroom and consequently their products. In a nut shell, good performance among learners can be affirmed and assured through the teachers' methods of teaching informed by their training modes. That is, the quality in the job performance of teachers who remain the major source of knowledge in the classroom can be measured by the learners' performance. It is believed that one of the major factors which influence teachers' performance in the classroom is the mode of training they received. This implies that a teacher's job performance depends on the quality of training gone through whether the sandwich or full-time training mode.

The 7th edition of the Nigeria Policy on Education (2014) further states that nation's philosophy of education. It is based on the belief that education is to be qualitative, comprehensive, functional and relevant to the needs of the society. It also spelt out the specific goal of education (among others) as to ensure the quality of education delivery at all levels. All these can be better achieved through the instrumentation of well-trained teachers either through their written documents or verbal expression. It is therefore glaring that the achievement of education objectives in any given society depends greatly on the effort of teachers. This implies that, teachers' impact can make or mar the education of learners and consequently the progress of a whole society. Angonjam & Sarungba

(2015) averred teachers are the backbone of the educational system, maker of the mankind and architect of the society. Although, it will not be objective to ascribe learner's achievement to only one factor, yet, the teacher forms the nucleus of any successful classroom teaching-learning process.

Since teachers are trained to improve the development of education in the country, then the mode of training them should be of paramount importance to the governments and all other education stakeholders. Fafunwa (1969) as cited in Siraj et al. (2023) is of the opinion that the quality of development of any nation is largely determined by the quality of her teachers and teacher education programme. It is a fact that poorly trained teachers would likely produce poor professionals in all fields of learning including teaching itself in future. It is then required that teachers are trained through appropriate and effective modes if the set educational objectives are to be achieved. To this effect, there are therefore two modes for the training of teachers in higher institutions of learning: the full-time mode and the sandwich mode.

However, the controversial acclaimed fallen standard of Education in the country has been attributed partly to poor job performance by teachers. This is believed to have taken root from the mode of training of such teachers. Based on this assumption, it then becomes imperative to carry out some investigations on the mode of training of teachers and the resultant effect on their job performance in Ondo State public primary schools.

Teachers' Job Performance

Performance could be defined as doing things according to the set objective. It could also be described as accomplishment of designated task. Some researchers have come out with a similar opinion. Olaniyan (2021), described performance as the ability to combine skillfully the right behaviour toward the achievement of organizational goals and objectives. Performance was also defined by Zaini et al. (2023) as an act of accomplishing or executing a given task. Job performance is defined as an aggregate of employee behaviours that have some expected value to organization either positive or negative (Emefiele, 2023). Additionally, Tsauri (2022) perceived performance as the total expected value to the organization of the discrete behavioural episode that an individual carries out over a specific period of time. Teachers' job performance can therefore be described as the accomplishment of designated tasks (teaching-learning process) by a teacher at a given period of time. Teachers' job performance can also be measured by the ability of a teacher to carry out his given responsibilities at a particular time focusing on the school's general objective as an educational organization. Kelechi (2020) described teachers' performance as the duties performed by a teacher at a particular period in the school system in achieving organizational goals. Teachers' job performance as opined by Elujekwute and Shir (2021) is the measurement of the quality of instruction given to learners by teachers in the school which is the rightly intended accomplishment of the school.

In addition, teacher's job performance can be rated excellent when he is able to inculcate permanent literacy and numeracy, and the ability to communicate; use character and moral training and the development of sound attitudes; develop in the child the ability to adapt to his or her changing environment among others, as contained in the Nigeria National Policy on Education (2004). All these are achievable through the training modes of teachers.

What is Training?

According to Loyalkas et al. (2019), training is the process of learning the skills that you need to do a job. Wikipedia encyclopedia (2010) also describes training as the acquisition of knowledge, skills and competencies as a result of the teaching of vocational or practical skills and knowledge that relate to specific use of competencies. Similarly, Santos (2022) identified training as an organized procedure by which people learn knowledge or skills for a definite purpose. In the same vein, training has been described as the systematic application of formal processes to help to acquire the knowledge and skills necessary for them to perform their job satisfactorily. It is also regarded as the basic function of human resource management (Armstrong at al., 2020). It has also been regarded as the basic function of human resource management (Yimam, 2022). Training can therefore be defined as the process of inculcating in the trainees, the necessary skills, knowledge, moral, behaviours and right attitude towards preparing them for productive and profitable performance of their assigned responsibilities in congruent with the organization's goals and objectives. Teachers' training mode is a process by which prospective teachers are being equipped with necessary skills, knowledge and behaviour useful for imparting other people's lives. This will ensure their all-round development and excellent performance at their duty posts. Because of its importance, training is carried out in different worlds of work using different approaches in order to achieve the set objectives of an organization. Therefore, the training of teachers is important if the education objectives are going to be achieved and government policy on education implemented. Oluoch and Gogo argued that, teachers are the pivot for the implementation of any education policy. Onukwu et al. (2020) also supported the fact that teachers serve as implementers of educational programmes at the classroom level.

Importance of Training

According to Ventista and Brown (2023), training of teachers and employees generally are imperative for equipping the trainees/worker with the required skills for better performance at work; developing in the trainees' the right attitude to work; improving the quality of job by the employee(s); enhancing more knowledge acquisition in the service area such that lead to competence in the worker; and helping to achieve organizational goals better and faster. Additionally, Khan and Abdullah (2019)

affirmed that teachers' training brings about the development of self-confidence and ability to conduct the class properly and impart the learners appropriately. It also brings about teachers' effectiveness and efficiency that results in proficiency and expertise in their job delivery. It as well helps to updates the teacher with new innovation such that aids him to impart the students with up-to-date education information. Apart from thee, Gunarathne et al. (2021) stated the importance of training as addressing performance gaps: that is, training and development allows the organization to address challenges faced by employees and then direct the training to solving the problem by creating areas for improvement and ensuring employee satisfaction. Training fosters sense of belonging and contentment in the employees. This could be achieved by optimising workforce potential and enhancing organisational productivity. Addressing training as an integral part of education, Fashiku, Jembola and Ayoku view teachers as custodian of knowledge who help the learners through various techniques to comprehend educational instruction and to be academically more competent and independent. The researchers further established the fact that training produces outcomes such as intellectual ability, skills and attitudes to be demonstrated by the learner at the end of the training period. To achieve the above stated facts therefore requires that teachers are well-equipped through quality education under a well supervised learning condition. This is hoped to produce in them the required proficiency towards excellence in their job performance.

Types of Modes of Training of Teachers

The two training modes under consideration in this study are:

- i) the sandwich training mode; and
- ii) the full-time training mode

The Sandwich Training Mode

The sandwich programme is a mode of training which was established to supplement the traditional method of delivering educational instruction to the Nigerian public. It is a study programme which involves the training of teachers already on the job on part time basis also a training for the young school leavers who lacked the opportunity of attending regular schools due to the challenge of sponsorship. In other words, some students who have gotten an initial training through which they have secured jobs which they would not like to leave for fear of being laid off, do go through the sandwich mode. This they do trying to upgrade their knowledge towards job upliftment or promotion at their work place. Chukwuemerie et al. (2025) supported this by stating that just as the young school leavers aspire for higher educational qualifications so also workers who for reasons such as professional upliftment, improvement of social and economic status among others seek higher qualifications in the colleges of education and universities. Hence, the introduction of open Universities which currently operates in many of the major cities in Nigeria is relevant. It is an additional means of obtaining training in Education through the sandwich system.

There are usually contact sessions when the student teachers come together for lectures, tutorials, counseling and practical training. The programme was introduced in the middle of 1980s in order to create opportunities for working class students of different levels such as: school certificate holders seeking grade II certificate, grade II certificate holders seeking Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE), and the holders of NCE seeking to obtain the Degree Certificate in Education. Presently there is sandwich or part-time programme for obtaining higher degrees in education and some other fields of study. The contact session is usually the school vacation period when the normal school academic work is suspended. This is so, to avoid disruption of school programme and to give room for the student teachers' concentration on their studies. Kayode and Adedokun (2019) asserted that sandwich programmes in Nigeria, date back to the mid-1980s. They are programmes that are run during the school vacations to create opportunities for teachers seeking to upgrade their qualifications, as well as for adults seeking career advancement or a change in profession.

The importance of sandwich programmes cannot be underrated because of its profound advantage in helping many teachers in acquiring better teaching skills in their fields of study and as well obtain higher education certificate. This was also observed by Udell et al. (2023) that promoting teachers' effectiveness through sandwich degree programmes in Nigeria Universities has broadened the knowledge of teachers in their subject areas. In Nigeria, the educators and organizers of these sandwich programmes are usually Colleges of Education or Universities that provide them study centers either within or outside the Universities premises. Professional skills obtained during this kind of training have been found to assist in awakening the dormant skills in the beneficiaries and so improve their job performance (Anurugwo, 2020). In some cases, this on-the-job training has led to healthy competition among the teachers who are found displaying the acquired skills during the classroom teaching-learning process. It therefore makes the concerned teachers more competent and up-to-date in discharging their duties. In congruent with this, Ehinola and Akomolafe (2022) observed that through sandwich programme, information is now easily accessible at fast speed, and that many more people can have the benefit of information and education.

The Full-Time Training Mode

The full-time training mode is the conventional programme which involves the meeting together of the learners and the tutor in the four walls of the classroom on regular basis. The learners and the teachers in this system usually have a face-to-face interaction where the contents of the course of study are discussed. Here, the students have the freedom to ask questions from their tutors. The classroom interaction continues regularly until the completion of the course of study. New skills and deeper knowledge of the course of study are gained through this medium. The system also permits the learners to make researches on the courses to be taught even

before the class holds. This goes a long way to develop professional skills in the learners faster and better than when they had a very limited time to run or brush through many numbers of courses.

The full-time training mode gives room for the teaching and demonstration of one teaching skill at a time. This gives room for easy digestion of a concept and sufficient time for practical before another skill is been introduced. It also gives way for systematic arrangement of the course contents in such a way that the teacher moves from known to unknown, simple to complex and from theory to practical. This makes the teaching real and acquisition of knowledge very easy. This was affirmed by Sardar et al. (2022) that, in regular teacher training institutes, to develop teaching skills, one skill is demonstrated at a time by a teacher educator and later on practiced by student teachers in reduced class size and time. The method according to the researchers¹, gives room for easy assimilation of new concept and retention of teaching skills. Peradventure, this was the reason for their ability to prepare lesson note better and in a more comprehensible manner. This is in line with Akinwumi and Adeyanju (2011) who empirically established that the full-time N.C.E. graduate teachers were better in lesson note preparation. The full-time trained teachers obtain their training from the formal institutions found all over the country. These conventional institutions are responsible for providing quality education through qualified tutors for the trainees who possess the necessary requirements. Gbadeyan (2009) also posited that the full-time mode of education is very popular and equally available in all parts of the world.

The National Teachers' Institute and the Distance Education

The National Teachers' Institute, Kaduna was established by the Federal Government in 1976 in order to enhance educational development. The purpose of establishing this institution was mainly the training of teachers for effectiveness through the distance learning mode. The country's urgent need for educated and competent teaching staff at all levels of educational system was the reason for this move (Daly, 2023). The Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE) distance education programme which was organized and coordinated by the National Teachers' Institute (NTI) is an important aspect of training of teachers in Nigeria. Thousands of teachers have been trained through this NTI in order to bridge the gap created by lack of sufficient trained teachers in the country and as well upgrade the teachers on the job. Yusuf (2022) reported this in his work that the NTI had about 600 study centers nationwide and has graduated up to 21,000 Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) candidates between 1990 and 1992. As reported by Ikegulu and Oranusi (2014), distance education is feasible over a broad geographical area. It enables students to obtain the necessary education without disrupting the life and work of students. Besides, it has helped in transforming serving Grade Two teachers into NCE holders. Indeed, between 1990 and 1996, the National Teachers' Institute was able to upgrade 24,817 serving Grade II teachers to the Nigeria Certificate in Education level (Adeola 2007). The NCE holders were also upgraded to degree holders in education through this NTI educational programme.

On the other hand, some researchers came out with the view that the programme is not as effective as expected. This they perceived to be so looking at the level of resource input and at times, the quality of output. Some of the reasons these researchers gave for this include inadequacy of teaching/learning facilities, resource materials, resource personnel coupled with poor learning environment. The assertion according to Oguntimehin (2009) was that, since the inception of National Teachers' Institute programmes, administrators have been throwing searchlight into the programme. They were querying the quality of the output (Nigeria Certificate in Education graduates), more so, as they doubt the adequacy of resources inputs into the programmes.

Distance Education and Open Universities

Education seems to be the bedrock of development in any society. This has gained serious attention from many people so that the population of scholars greatly increases yearly. Coombs and DeLuca (2021) suggested that many countries in the world today need educational systems capable of handling very large students' populations of 100,000 and more. The unfortunate thing is that the government cannot afford the fund to finance the establishment and maintenance of sufficient number of institutions to cater for the increasing number of students every year especially at the higher education level. This was observed by Osaat and Nsereka (2012) that the government in both developed and developing countries no longer have the money to erect and maintain buildings for such large number of students in a year. Therefore, since this demand cannot be silenced looking at the importance of education in the nation's development, then there is a need to proffer solution to this seemingly great problem of the society. The distance education programme with open University being but one of the approaches easily accessible by many, therefore, stands to bridge the gap.

The implementation was in line with the Nigeria National Policy on Education (2004) and (2014), which made provision for a national open university. The open university has therefore provided a complimentary means for training more teachers in the country. The provision was made to ensure that there are more hands in the teaching sector to meet special needs of employers and employees. Researchers have observed that open distance learning had been used as pre-teacher preparation method and that the training method has increased the quality of classroom teaching (Burns 2011; Bof 2014). Kudakwashe and Richard (2013) also affirmed that training of teachers through open and distance learning (ODL) is not a new phenomenon. Distance education has paved way for many selected or unreached parts of the society to obtain higher education. As postulated by Undiyaundeye (2001), distance education gives room for access to higher education to a barred segment of society. Today, the distance education or distance learning has upgraded to online education where the learners and teachers meet virtually. At times, the class is purely online through zoom or video call. Sometimes it comes as a combination of online and conventional classroom depending on how it is

organized by the institution or the teacher in charge. In this digital age, it is noteworthy that many online classes exist where different topics related to life and career are taught to learners at various levels of education. Besides, various online classes are available where knowledge and skills are imparted to learners towards creativity and improved potentiality. Technology therefore, has transformed the distance education making it an exciting place to learn new things, collaborate with others and retain self-discipline and also, it is majorly responsible for the current global education advancement (Yusuf, 2022; Fashiku et al, 2022).

Training Mode and Teacher's Job Performance

Generally, training of employees is an important strategy used by organizations to develop their employees towards improving capability in their job delivery. According to Elnaga and Imran (2013), training is a necessity in the workplace. Training of teachers provides opportunity for them to build on their skills and knowledge and so enhances better performances in disseminating educational instruction to learners in the classroom. Training also increases effectiveness and efficiency among teachers thus improving the productivity of the school. Training can also bring out the latent potentials in teachers and as well equip them with the best strategy to utilize these. Training of teachers is expected to be a continuous exercise as it encourages more skill acquisition, updates the teachers and familiarizes them the more with education objectives. This enables these teachers to collaborate with the school administrator with the achievement of the set goal in mind. For the mission and vision of an organization to remain achievable, continuous learning environment needs to be made available for the workforce (Njideka and Ibeto, 2020). The presence of trained and competent teachers in the school helps to raise a high standard for the school and increase teachers' morale. Hence, the benefits of training teachers include: increased knowledge and skill acquisition; potential discovery and profitable utilization of acquired skills; higher academic standard; increased teachers' morale; increasing productivity i. e. production of well-equipped learners; enhancement of job delivery; increased competence in subject matter mastery and so forth (Ehinola & Akomolafe, 2022). It is also worthy of note that despite the effectiveness of the two training modes under investigation, a close observation shows some disparities between the two. These include the study time/contact period, place, quality of students/teachers/education, level of students' attentiveness and so forth. This is in line with Aghahowa and Omoregbe (2021) that the content of full-time and sandwich appear to be the same but a closer examination will prove that both programmes are not in parity. The researchers further explained that differences exist in terms of the quality of students admitted, duration/ contact periods and hours, the quality and effort put in by lecturer, poor remuneration of sandwich staff, access to infrastructure among others. All the above show a notable difference that exists between the full-time and sandwich training modes. It is glaring that the sandwich training mode received less resources than the full-time training mode and vice versa. This might lead to the production of quality products by the latter with all the necessary resources in place.

However, some researchers have carried out investigations on certain factors that affect employee's job performance. After reviewing some studies, it was discovered that factors such as, age, experience, salary, education background, working condition and job satisfaction affected employee's performance and not training alone. Based on this findings, Kuranchie-Mensah and Amponsah-Tawiah (2016) opined that it has been found out that several factors affect employee's performance.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to compare teachers' modes of training and their job performance in Ondo State public primary schools.

The specific objectives of this study are to:

- (i) investigate the proportion of teachers who passed through the sandwich training and full-time training in Ondo State public primary schools from 2015 to 2025; and
- (ii) examine the teachers' level of effectiveness in terms of mastery of subject matter and use of instructional materials in Ondo State primary schools

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

- (iii) What is the proportion of teachers who passed through the sandwich training and full-time training in Ondo State public primary schools from 2015 to 2025?
- (iv) What is the teachers' level of effectiveness in terms of mastery of subject matter and use of instructional materials in Ondo State primary schools?

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study adopted the descriptive survey research design using the quantitative approach. The population of the study comprised all the 11,891 teachers of public primary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria. The study sample comprised 384 teachers, who were selected using purposive sampling from 24 public primary schools in the study area. Simple random sampling technique was used to select four schools each from six Local Government Areas (LGAs) selected from the three existing senatorial districts in Ondo state. That is, two LGAs from each senatorial district. Furthermore, 16 teachers were selected from each school using purposive sampling technique based on their modes of training.

Two research instruments were used to collect data for the study. A self-designed Questionnaire titled Teachers' Mode of Training and their Job Performance (TMTJP) which was used to obtain information on the bio-data of the respondents as well as their mode of training and job performance. The questionnaire consisted of statement on 4-pointed Likert scale where teachers were to tick the right alternative such as Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD).

The second instrument used was the Teachers' Effectiveness Observation Schedule (TEOS) which was used to observe and rate the teachers while teaching in their classes in the selected schools. This observation was based on their effectiveness in the mastery of subject matter and use of instructional materials in the process of teaching. The observation schedule was adapted from the Faculty of Education Obafemi Awolowo University Ile-Ife, Nigeria. The data obtained was used to examine the level of effectiveness of both the sandwich and full-time teachers in their job delivery especially in terms of mastery of subject matter and use of instructional materials. The instruments were validated before usage. Percentages and mean scores were used to analyze the research questions raised.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: What is the proportion of teachers who passed through the sandwich training and full-time training in Ondo State public primary schools?

Table 1: Percentage Analysis of the Proportion of Teachers who passed through Sandwich Training and Full-time Training in Ondo State Primary Schools from 2015 to 2025

S/N	Proportion of trained teachers	No of Respondents	Percentage Analysis
1	Number of teachers who passed through the full-time training mode	243	63.28
2	Number of teachers who passed through the sandwich training mode	141	36.72
Total number of respondents		384	100.00

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Figure 1. Proportion of Trained Teachers in Ondo State Primary Schools from 2015 to 2025

Table 1 and figure 1 above show the percentage analysis of the proportion of teachers that passed through Sandwich Training and Full-time Training in Ondo State public primary schools from 2015 to 2025. The result shows that out of the 384 respondents, 243 (63.28%) were found to have passed through training on full-time basis. Also, the result reveals that 141 (36.72%) of the respondents passed through training on sandwich basis. The finding therefore, implies that majority of the teachers 63.28% passed through full-time training while a significant proportion 36.72% of the respondents passed through sandwich training. This is in agreement with Owolabi (2007) who posited that, the government should find all possible means to retain veteran and experienced (that is, already

trained) teachers who are still willing to serve so that they can contribute their wealth of experience to improving the system. On the other hand, as reported by Yusuf (2022) the NTI pivotal teachers programme produced 19,025; 20,800; and 15,567 qualified teachers for year 2000, 2001 and 2002 respectively. The implication of this is that both the full-time trained and the sandwich trained teachers contribute significantly to promoting education especially in the study area.

Research Question 2: What is the teachers' level of effectiveness in terms of mastery of subject matter and use of instructional materials in Ondo State primary schools?

Table 2: Percentage Analysis of Teachers' Level of Effectiveness in terms of Mastery of Subject Matter and Use of Instructional Materials in Ondo State primary schools

S/N	Teachers' level of effectiveness in terms of mastery of subject matter and use of instructional materials	Range of Scores	Number of Teachers	Percentage Analysis	Remarks
1	Full-time trained teachers	70-100	104	48.83%	Excellent
		60-69	109	30.05%	V. Good
		50-59	64	15.02%	Good
		40-49	32	4.23%	Fair
		0-39	09	1.38%	Poor
2	Sandwich Trained teachers	70-100	53	48.53%	Excellent
		60-69	54	31.58%	V. Good
		50-59	25	14.62%	Good
		40-49	07	4.09%	Fair
		0-39	02	1.17%	Poor

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Figure 2: The Full-Time Trained Teachers in Ondo State Primary Schools

Figure 3: The Sandwich Trained Teachers in Ondo State Primary Schools

Table 2 and figures 1 and 2 show the percentage analysis of teachers' level of effectiveness in terms of mastery of subject matter and use of instructional materials in Ondo State primary schools, based on the categorization on the type of training received (full-time and sandwich programmes). The results showed that out of the 243 (100%) of the full-time teachers rated, 104(48.83%) scored within the range of 70 and 100, which was clarified as "Excellent". Besides, 109(30.05%) of the full-time teachers scored between 60 and 69 (Very Good). Equally, 64(15.02%) of the full-time teachers scored between 50 and 59 (Good). Furthermore, 32(4.23%) of the teachers scored between 40 and 49 (Fair); while 09(1.38%) of the teachers scored between 0 and 39 (Poor) respectively. The implication is that substantial proportions of full-time trained teachers possess a strong mastery of subject matter and effectiveness in the utilisation of instructional materials in the classroom.

In the same vein, the analysis shows that out of the 141(100%) sandwich teachers rated, 53(48.53%) scored within the range of 70 and 100, which was clarified as "Excellent". Also, 54(31.58%) of the sandwich teachers scored between 60 and 69 (Very Good). Equally, 25(14.62%) of the sandwich teachers scored between 50 and 59 (Good). Furthermore, 07(4.09%) of the sandwich teachers scored between 40 and 49 (Fair); while 02(1.17%) of the sandwich teachers scored between 0 and 39 (Poor) respectively. The implication is that substantial proportions of sandwich trained teachers possess a strong mastery of subject matter and effectiveness in the utilisation of instructional materials in the classroom.

A careful observation from the Table shows that the full-time trained teachers slightly outperformed their sandwich counterparts in all categories with marginal differences. Based on this analysis, it can be inferred that the percentage distribution across the two categories of teachers, full-time and sandwich-trained teachers reveals a consistently high level of effectiveness in terms of mastery of subject matter and use of instructional materials in Ondo State primary schools.

The finding is in line with Jegede (2011); Ogundele and Sofoluwe (2012); and Etejere and Ogundele (2008) who opined that the training of student teachers made use of the same curriculum, syllabus, methods and instructional facilities. Equally, the products were not trained in different ways which means that, the products of the institutions were trained equally for the benefit of the society. This is contrary to the findings of Ojo (1979) who carried out a study on the development of part time studies at the University of Lagos and found that full-time students at the University of Lagos at the period covered by his study performed better than the part time students. Similarly, Aghahowa and Omoregbe (2021) argue that the content of full-time and sandwich appear to be the same but a closer examination will prove that both programmes are not in parity. The researchers further explained that differences exist in terms of the quality of students admitted, duration/ contact periods and hours, the quality and effort put in by lecturers and so forth.

4. CONCLUSION

The study empirically establishes that the full-time trained teachers are more in number than the sandwich trained teachers; the full-time trained teachers slightly outperformed their sandwich counterparts in all categories with marginal differences, but with a consistently high level of effectiveness in terms of mastery of subject matter and use of instructional materials in Ondo State primary schools. The slight outperformance of full-time trained teachers over their sandwich counterparts in Ondo State primary schools may be attributed to the structured and immersive nature of full-time teacher education programmes, which offer more rigorous

academic exposure, supervised teaching practice, and continuous engagement with current pedagogical methods. In contrast, sandwich programmes are often characterized by intermittent sessions and condensed curricula, which may limit the depth of content mastery and hands-on experience with instructional resources. By implication, the methods and materials employed by the teacher to communicate education instruction to learners has significant influence on the teacher's job performance as well the students' academic performance.

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